

First records of *Neoscona kisangani* Grasshoff, 1986 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: We present the first records of the spider *Neoscona kisangani* Grasshoff, 1986 from South Africa. The species was described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The general morphology of live specimens based on photographs is provided, with notes on their distribution.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Neoscona* Simon, 1864 is a large genus known from 124 species and 11 subspecies with a wide geographical distribution (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The African *Neoscona* species were revised by Grasshoff (1986) and a review of the 17 species recorded from South Africa was presented by Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2022). Data on the South African species was obtained during surveys undertaken as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2015).

The first record of *Neoscona kisangani* Grasshoff, 1986 from South Africa is a female sampled from the Eastern Cape Province by the first author. The epigyne correspond with that of *N. kisangani*. The female of *N. kisangani* can be distinguished by its extremely short scapus, small posteriorly directed copulatory openings, and copulatory ducts that run inward and appear laterally as translucent dark stripes (Figs 5 & 6).

The type series of *N. kisangani* was sampled from Kisangani and the Garamba National Park in the Democratic Republic of Congo. Since then, no further information on the species has been published. According to Grasshoff (1986) *N. kisangani* resemble *N. quincasea* Roberts, 1983. They can also be confused with the smaller specimens of *N. subfusca* (C.L. Koch, 1837) which have similar abdominal humps that are usually absent in larger specimens. Ventrally the abdomen is uniformly pale, unlike the darker, patterned ventrum of *N. quincasea* and *N. subfusca*.

TAXONOMY

Neoscona kisangani Grasshoff, 1986

Neoscona kisangani Grasshoff, 1986: 28, f. 31-35 (Dmf).

Diagnostic characteristics: Female: TL 5.0–6.0 mm. Abdomen almost as wide as it is long, with shoulder humps (Figs 1–4). Dorsal abdomen with wedge-shaped spot and folium pattern (Figs 1 & 3). Low contrast, overall pale. Ventral side uniformly pale, ventral abdomen medially barely darkened. Legs banded (Figs 1 & 4). Epigyne scapus is extremely short, not bent toward the base; openings small, directed aboral. Vulval ducts initially run inward behind the openings, thus visible from the side as translucent dark stripes (Figs 5 & 6). Male: 3.5–4.5 mm. Legs: Tibia I prolateral with a longer spine, about one-third the length of the entire leg segment. Tibia II ventral-prolateral with about 10 shorter spines, with the apical quarter free of spines. Palp with terminal lamella with a prominent hook. Terminal apophysis narrow and leaf-like thin (Grasshoff, 1986).

Figures 1–6. *Neoscona kisangani* female. 1. Line drawing of the female habitus dorsal view. 2. Abdomen. 3. Ventral view. 4. Female dorsal view (alcohol). 5. Line drawings of different views of the epigyne. 6. Epigyne of alcohol specimen. Credits: 4 & 6. Ruan Booysen. 1–3 & 5. After Grasshoff (1986).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, South Africa (first record).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Neoscona kasangani* is currently known only from two localities in South Africa, in the Eastern and Western Cape (Fig. 7). The species is known only from females, and is probably under-sampled because they can easily be confused with other orb-web spiders. It is expected to occur in more African countries. The species was sampled from the Grassland and Succulent Karoo biomes.

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